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*Corresponding Author:
**Collins Iyaminapu
Iyoloma**
Department of Electrical
Engineering, Rivers State
University, Nigeria

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Continual Neural Learning Computational Method for In-Ear based User Authentication Systems

Collins Iyaminapu Iyoloma*
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Rivers State University, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Biometric authentication plays an important role in many emerging security solutions and as such presents an active area of research. In particular, biometric applications that employ some sort of neural artificial intelligence solution are becoming more prominent in the security and access control field. However, how best to learn the important (salient) biometric features particularly with respect to a streaming set of data makes it more challenging for existing neural techniques. This research paper presents bio-inspired neural computational technique that is of a progressive nature (learns continually) for the task of in-person prediction. The technique specifically employs an emerging Continual Neural Learning (CNL) technique to predict the authenticity of a person. For this prediction task, simulations are performed by feeding continual streams of in-ear biometric data obtained from a real world subject to the CNL technique which predicts the likelihood of a valid or invalid feature pattern. The results of simulations are reported in terms of the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and validated using two progressive (continual) learning approaches - an existing approach called the progressive Long Short-Term Memory (pLSTM) and an emerging approach called the Neuronal Auditory Machine Intelligence (NeuroAMI). From the results, it was found that the NeuroAMI gave best MAPE error estimates considering 3 different random data corruption trials. Hence, the NeuroAMI is recommended as a candidate CNL approach for in-ear authentication systems.

Keywords:- AI, biometric, continual learning, in-ear, in-person, prediction

INTRODUCTION

In modern society, secure and safe access plays a key role in many operations such as found in the trading and e-commerce, Personal Computing (PC), healthcare sector and governmental institutes. Indeed, the enhancement in security enabled smart PC devices is the introduction of the biometric feature or function. A primary challenge in the research community is how to effectively and more efficiently harness the power of biometrics in effectively authenticating genuine users of PC gadgets in the face of possible biometric access data breaches or corruptions either intentional by a hacker or due systemic biometric access data corruptions.[8,9]

Existing and highly popular biometrics such as facial and fingerprint are well applied and have shown promising results; but it has been reported in several studies the information breach problem in the aforementioned biometrics making them in-effective system solutions in highly sensitive applications such as banking and finance [5,7]. A promising alternative to existing biometric user authentication solutions is the in-ear biometrics.

However, in the field of in-ear biometric authentication, there are limited research studies in the use of Continual Neural Learning (CNL) methods to train the captured data for in-person prediction. To perform in-person prediction is to determine the possibility of whether the next sampled trait is an anomaly (invalid) or non-anomalous (valid). This is particularly useful in situations where frequent interruptions to authenticated access need to be detected such as in bank ATM channels or smart organizations.

In this research paper, we study the potentials of two CNL methods for the task of in-person prediction.

RELATED STUDIES

The field of biometrics authentication is indeed a very active one with a great deal of research on going in diverse scientific computing areas [4]. In particular, the successful applications in security access control (Ikponnwoosa et al., 2023) and forensic monitoring systems[19] have been reported. The success of such systems is largely attributed to the enhancement and development of pattern recognition algorithms in addition to advancement in computing hardware – particularly in the field of wearable's [25].

Some emerging areas of applications include but not limited to gesture recognition biometrics [18,19], body skeleton monitoring biometrics (Ibrahim et al., 2016; Li et al., 2016), and behavioural continuous authentication biometrics (Lane et al., 2010; Shi et al., 2011; Murmura et al., 2015; Patel et al., 2016).

The emerging field of in-ear biometrics has more recently regained renewed attention. The in-ear biometrics is an alternative but more ideal non-invasive tamper proof solution that exploits the unique property of the human auditory canal to build more stable representations of a person. The research studies conducted in (Arakawa et al., 2016; Alsawaf & Chaczko, 2020) have shown that the use of in-ear biometrics is a promising option for user authentication.

However, it is still a matter of continuous investigation to validate the efficacy of in-ear biometrics for real-time in-person prediction during an authentication session. In particular, the capability of alternative neural pattern recognition solutions that are based on the Continual Neural Learning (CNL) strategy is lacking in the field of in-ear biometrics based in-person prediction for user authentication.

Hence, this research attempts to fill this gap by proposing a novel CNL solution that can be applied to in-person prediction.[1-15]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data Processing

For the purpose of this research, real-time streaming in-ear biometric data of two subjects are considered where the first subject represents an authentic (valid) user

while the second represents the invalid or corrupting user. For a given subject, at least three simulation captures are performed to obtain the raw data and this data is processed accordingly to obtain several important statistics such as the maximum (max), minimum (min), and the average (avg) of the input data. The processed data is then averaged to obtain the single representational statistic for the given subject as modelled in Eq.1.

$$M_s = \mu \begin{pmatrix} \max(I_{data}) \\ \min(I_{data}) \\ \mu(I_{data}) \\ \sigma(I_{data}) \end{pmatrix} \tag{1}$$

Where,

I_{data} = input data pattern for a given subject, in Hz

max = maximum of I_{data}

min = minimum of I_{data}

μ = mean of I_{data}

σ = variance of I_{data}

The parameter, I_{data} , in Eq,1 represents the peaks of the signal patterns obtained from a dynamic simulation model interface as shown in Figure 1. This model interface in conjunction with an in-ear device embedded to ears of the subjects (Subjects 1 and 2) is employed to synthesize the required input data.

Fig.1:-Dynamic Model for Generating Feature Patterns

The data in the authentic averaged representational solution for Subject 1 is replicated 90 times to simulate repeated user authentication and then corrupted using the representational solution of the second subject (Subject 2) which is replicated 10 times. Hence, this gives a total feature sample of 100 sequences.

The concatenated data (Subject 1 and Subject 2) are form a mixed data representation which is at least 10 times more than the number of feature attributes i.e. 10 times the pre-computed data statistics (Alwosheel et al., 2018). A sample of the estimated statistic for the 2 subjects is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1:-Feature Statistics of Two Subjects

Subject ID	Max (Hz)	Min (Hz)	μ (Hz)	σ (Hz)
1	37	0	23	16
2	22	-1	10	8

To simulate sensory data variation, the feature pattern representations of the combined subjects are randomized with respect to their relative indexes such that approximate new feature sets are replicated. This is useful for emulating the capturing process as expected from real person(s) behaviours.

CNL Data Processing

In this research, two Continual Neural Learning (CNL) methods are employed for the task of predicting the next feature representation.

The first method called the progressive Long Short-Term Memory (pLSTM) is based on earlier study on using continual learning ideologies such as iterative (recurrent) task sharing between primary and secondary LSTMs to evolve a better representational model of the world (Fayek, 2017).[16-25]

The second method is called the Auditory CNL net (AudCNLnet) which is based on the Neuronal Auditory Machine Intelligence (NeuroAMI) - an emerging CNL based on the work introduced recently in (Osegi & Anireh, 2020; Osegi, 2023). The AudCNLnet technique exploits some of the key findings in auditory cortex including the concept of Mismatch Negativity Effect (MMN) and sparse frequency-tuned neuron activity. It specifically uses the algorithmic strategy proposed in (Osegi, 2023).

The concept of processing either by the pLSTM or AudCNLnet is as shown in Figure 2. For the pLSTM recurrent processing is performed to enable the learning of long-range context while the AudCNLnet learns in feed-forward manner based on sparse activating deviant neurons. The parameters of the pLSTM and AudCNLnet used in this research are as provided in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Fig.2:-CNL Processing for in-ear user authentication

To predict a valid or authentic user, the dynamic in-ear biometric neural data processing is performed as shown in Figure 2. The idea in this research study is to extract the peaks of combined channel signals (both left and right) and parse the data to a dynamic text storage file for

continual signal processing by the CNL processor. The data for CNL processing is achieved for several numbers of capture trials (N_{ctr}) and considering a specified simulation time, t_s , as shown in the flowchart of Figure 3.

Fig.3:-Feature Data Processing for in-ear user authentication

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Simulations are performed in the MATLAB programming language and using default CNL operating parameters. The results are reported in terms of the MAPE which is a suitable performance evaluation metric for continual learning systems.

For all simulation trials, we follow the small data learning paradigm where 30%

of input feature data is used for continual learning during training while the remaining 70% for continual testing.

Simulation Results using AudCNLnet

In this case and following from the data processing methodology outlined in Section 3 (see sub-section 3.2), three different (corrupted) input in-ear feature data is generated (see Tables 2 to 4).

Table 2:-Corrupted Feature Statistics for Trial Dataset 1 (Only first 10 samples shown)

Pattern No	Max (Hz)	Min (Hz)	μ (Hz)	σ (Hz)
1	37	0	23	37
2	37	0	23	37
3	37	0	23	37
4	37	0	23	37
5	37	0	23	37
6	37	0	23	37
7	37	0	23	37
8	37	0	23	37
9	37	0	23	37
10	22	-1	10	22

Table 3:-Corrupted Feature Statistics for Trial Dataset 2 (Only first 10 samples shown)

Pattern No	Max (Hz)	Min (Hz)	μ (Hz)	σ (Hz)
1	37	0	23	37
2	37	0	23	37
3	37	0	23	37
4	37	0	23	37
5	22	-1	10	22
6	37	0	23	37
7	37	0	23	37
8	37	0	23	37
9	37	0	23	37
10	37	0	23	37

Table.4:-Corrupted Feature Statistics for Trial Dataset 3 (Only first 10 samples shown)

Pattern No	Max (Hz)	Min (Hz)	μ (Hz)	σ (Hz)
1	22	-1	10	22
2	37	0	23	37
3	37	0	23	37
4	37	0	23	37
5	37	0	23	37
6	37	0	23	37
7	37	0	23	37
8	37	0	23	37
9	37	0	23	37
10	37	0	23	37

These data are fed to the AudCNLnet which firstly encodes the feature patterns, then performs continual prediction including a continual learning (training)

and testing phase. The corresponding encoding sequences for the three trial dataset samples provided in Tables 2 to 4 are as shown in Table 5.

Table 5:-Encoded Feature Patterns (Only first 10 samples shown)

Pattern No	Trial Data 1	Trial Data 2	Trial Data 3
1	16383	16383	16383
2	16383	16383	16383
3	16383	16383	16383
4	16383	16383	16383
5	16383	3788	3788
6	16383	16383	16383
7	16383	16383	16383
8	16383	16383	16383
9	16383	16383	16383
10	3788	16383	16383

As can be clearly seen, AudCNLnet is able to automatically encode the sequences into two classes of mixed integers – Class 16383 corresponding to the invalid or corrupt feature pattern and Class 3788 corresponding to the valid feature pattern.

These patterns are processed by the AudCNLnet continually to give predictions of the correct class.

The MAPE response plot for the 3 different random data corrupted in-ear feature pattern sequences is as shown in Figure 3.

Fig.4:-MAPE response plots of the AudCNLnet of generated feature patterns

The MAPE response shows the performance relatively improves with each increase sequence point. The zigzag graphic demonstrates the difficulty in the prediction process and the diversity in the data due to corruption. This diversity is dependent on the nature of data presented to the AudCNLnet.

Comparative Simulation Results with the pLSTM

To validate the efficacy of the AudCNLnet over conventional neural models, it is compared with the pLSTM. The numerical average MAPE results are as shown in Table 6.

Table 6:-Comparative Results – AudCNLnet vs. pLSTM

Trial Data	AudCNLnet	pLSTM
1	0.0490	6.5515
2	0.0588	6.4429
3	0.0490	6.7548
Average:	0.0523	6.5831

The average value clearly shows that the AudCNLnet will outperform the pLSTM which gave extremely high values for the given trial datasets. The pLSTM high MAPE values imply it is unsuitable for this particular task.

CONCLUSION

This research has presented a progressive or Continual Neural Learning (CNL) based approach for in-person prediction using in-ear biometric traits data. The focus had been on developing a robust and adaptive

model that can easily and more efficiently deal with the problem of predictive authentication.

The research has specifically investigated the potential of an auditory-inspired CNL network (AudCNLnet) method considering limited data features from 2 real individual subjects wherein data from one subject is corrupted by that of another and the task is to predict the valid or invalid subject feature.

For this particular task, The AudCNLnet is also compared to an existing more popular deep learning based CNL called the progressive Long Short-Term Memory (pLSTM). The results showed that the proposed AudCNLnet is able to give better predictions for the study data. Considering the comparative results, the AudCNLnet clearly outperforms the pLSTM in all considered trial datasets.

It will be interesting to investigate the impact of voice embeddings on the captured in-ear biometric traits and how the proposed CNL method can handle such effects. This remains a matter for future collaborative investigations.

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